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Ganglioside enriched molecule activity during trophectoderm specification.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here observation of ganglioside enriched molecule activity during trophectoderm specification in in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

Citations

1. Breimer, M.E., Säljö, K., Barone, A. and Teneberg, S., 2017. Glycosphingolipids of human embryonic stem cells. *Glycoconjugate journal*, 34(6), pp.713-723.